

Professional Integrity and Pedagogical Competence of Teachers With Leadership Mentoring As Moderator

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Abstract. The study aimed to look into the moderating effect of leadership mentoring on the interaction between professional integrity and pedagogical competence of teachers. In this study, the researcher selected 190 elementary school teachers in Kiblawan District in Davao del Sur as the respondents of the study. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, and Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that teachers' professional integrity, pedagogical competence, and managerial coaching for teachers were described as extensive. Further, partial correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between professional integrity and teachers' pedagogical competence when moderated by leadership mentoring. Evidently, regression analysis proved that leadership mentoring is a significant moderator of the interaction between professional integrity and teachers' pedagogical competence. The Department of Education (DepEd) may enhance teacher certification and licensing requirements to ensure that teachers meet high standards of competence and ethics.

KEY WORDS

1. professional integrity 2. pedagogical competence 3. leadership mentoring

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1. Introduction

Professional integrity and pedagogical competence are essential for teachers as they play a central role in shaping the quality of education and student experiences. Pedagogical competence ensures teachers have the knowledge and skills to deliver effective instruction. Competent teachers use research-based practices and teaching strategies that enhance student learning. More so, competent teachers can differentiate instruction to meet the diverse needs of students. They adapt their teaching methods to address various learning styles and abilities.

Teachers with professional integrity provide a foundation of ethical behavior and trust, while pedagogically competent teachers create effective and engaging learning environments that lead to improved student outcomes. These qualities are fundamental for the success of educational processes and the development of well-rounded, knowledgeable, and ethical citizens. The lack of pedagogical competence among teachers is a significant concern globally, affecting both developed and developing countries. In the US, many teacher preparation programs

are criticized for not providing sufficient practical training. New teachers often enter the profession with strong theoretical knowledge but lack the hands-on experience needed to manage classrooms effectively and implement diverse teaching strategies (Darling-Hammond, 2019). Similarly, Carver-Thomas and Darling-Hammond (2019) reported that high turnover rates among teachers lead to a loss of experienced educators and create a continuous influx of novice teachers who may lack pedagogical competence. This instability disrupts the learning environment and hinders the development of a strong pedagogical foundation. In many Asian countries, rapid educational reforms often outpace teachers' ability to adapt. These reforms frequently introduce new curricula and teaching methods without providing adequate training and support, leaving teachers underprepared (Tan, 2019). Also, Rahman and Pandian (2019) noted that resource limitations in many Asian countries mean that teachers often lack access to modern teaching materials, technology, and professional development opportunities. This hinders their ability to develop and apply effective pedagogical skills. In some parts of Asia, there is a strong emphasis on traditional, lecture-based teaching methods. This approach often leaves little room for innovative or student-centered pedagogies, limiting teachers' ability to engage students effectively and cater to diverse learning needs (Cheng Mok, 2020). In Vietnam, Nguyen and Nguyen (2019) noted that high student-teacher ratios in many Asian countries result in overcrowded classrooms, making it challenging for teachers to manage classrooms effectively and provide individualized attention, further exacerbating the lack of pedagogical competence. Taking things in the Philippine setting, Oracion and Magayon (2020) reported that one of the primary issues is insufficient pre-service and in-service training for teachers. Many teachers enter the profession without a strong foundation in effective teaching methods, classroom management, and curriculum design. Professional development opportunities are often limited and do not address the specific needs of teachers, leading to a persistent gap in pedagogical competence. Additionally, Ocampo (2021) noted that the curriculum in the Philippines is often criticized for being outdated and overly theoretical, with insufficient emphasis on practical and student-centered approaches. Teachers struggle to adapt their teaching methods to meet the demands of a curriculum that does not align with contemporary educational practices. Although studies have shown sufficient facts about the professional integrity and pedagogical competence of teachers, some issues have not yet been explored. There is a scarcity of research that specifically examines the moderating role of leadership mentoring in the interaction between faculty integrity and teachers' pedagogical competence. Thus, it is in this context that the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine context, particularly in the Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur, using a quantitative research design. Specifically, the researcher made use of hierarchical regression analysis to have a better understanding of the moderating effect of leadership mentoring on the interaction between professional integrity and the pedagogical competence of teachers, which is found to be scarce.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, respondents, ethics, instrument, procedure, data collection, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher employed quantitative research, specifically the descriptive-correlational technique through mediation analysis, to collect data, ideas, facts, and information relevant to the study. As defined by Ahmad et al. (2019), quantitative research methodologies and strategies systematically and impartially gathered and analyzed numerical data to understand phenomena, correlations, or trends. These methods involved statistical analysis to derive insights and draw conclusions from the data. Quantitative research entailed collecting and analyzing numerical data within a structured framework to explore various aspects of phenomena, relationships, or patterns. As noted by Mohajan (2020), descriptive research techniques encompassed methods used to depict, observe, and analyze the characteristics, behaviors, or phenomena of interest without manipulation or influence. The main goal was to provide a comprehensive portrayal of the subject under study, focusing on describing existing conditions rather than exploring causality. Additionally, descriptive research allows researchers to outline and characterize various attributes, traits, or features of a population, group, or phenomenon, including demographic details, behaviors, attitudes, and other relevant factors. As defined by Hassan (2024), correlational research design was a type of non-experimental research used to explore the relationship between two or more variables. This approach involved assessing the extent to which changes in one variable coincided with changes in another, without manipulating either variable. The objective was to determine whether a statistical correlation existed between the variables and to understand the direction and strength of this relationship. Correlational research served as a crucial tool for advancing knowledge in various fields by uncovering connections between variables, generating hypotheses, and informing practical applications and interventions. Moreover, Baron and Kenny (1986) defined moderation analysis through hierarchical regression as a statistical method used to determine whether the relationship between two variables (independent and dependent variables) is influenced by a third variable, known as the moderator. Hierarchical regression involves entering variables into the regression equation in steps or blocks, allowing researchers to assess the impact of adding new variables on the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. In the context of moderation analysis, hierarchical regression specifically examines how the inclusion of the moderator variable changes the strength or direction of the relationship between the primary independent variable and the dependent variable. This method helps identify if and how the moderator variable interacts with the independent variable to affect the outcome variable. Moderation analysis was suitable when researchers aimed to explore the relationships between variables and understand the underlying mechanisms. Hierarchical regression allows researchers to explore complex relationships between variables, including interactions between predictors. In this study, the primary interest is not only in the direct effects of professional integrity and leadership mentoring on pedagogical competence but also in understanding how leadership mentoring influences (moderates) the strength or direction of the relationship between professional integrity and pedagogical competence. The interest of the study was to investigate whether leadership mentoring significantly moderates the interaction between professional integrity and teachers' pedagogical competence.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were elementary school teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur. In this study, the 190 respondents were selected through stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling according to Leedy and Ormrod (2018) is a probabilistic sampling technique used in research to select a representative sam-

ple from a population by dividing it into subgroups or strata based on certain characteristics. Within each stratum, a random sample is drawn, and these samples are combined to create the final representative sample for the study. This method ensures that each subgroup is adequately represented in the sample, allowing for more accurate generalizations and inferences to be made about the entire population. Moreover, the primary consideration of this study was to select respondents who can provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those permanent-regular elementary school teachers in Kiblawan District in Davao del Sur, those who are not subjected to any administrative or criminal complaints, and those who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey

questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions and thus it did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of the teachers.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The study used adopted survey questionnaires to suit the current investigation. The questionnaire is composed of three parts. The first part is about the professional integrity of teachers. This questionnaire was distributed among the three indicators: ethical resilience, duty of integrity, and principle-based liability. The scale obtained a Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.934, which is described as excellent. The questionnaire made use a 5-point Likert scale and was determined based on the following ranges of means:

Range of Mean, Description, and Interpretation of Teachers’ Professional Integrity

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The professional integrity of teachers is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The professional integrity of teachers is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The professional integrity of teachers is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The professional integrity of teachers is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The professional integrity of teachers is never observed.

The second part of the instrument is about pedagogical competence of elementary school teachers. This questionnaire was indicated with pedagogic skills; teacher education management; ethically oriented practices; and pedagog-

ical endeavor. The scale obtained a Chronbach’s alpha value of 0.946 which is described as excellent. The questionnaire made use a 5-point Likert scale and was determined based on the following ranges of means:

The third part is about the leadership mentoring for teachers. The scale obtained a Chronbach’s alpha value of 0.932 which was de-

scribed as excellent. The questionnaire made use a 5-point Likert scale and was determined based on the following ranges of means:

Range of Mean, Description, and Interpretation of Teachers' Pedagogical Competence

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The pedagogical competence of teachers is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The pedagogical competence of teachers is often-times manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The pedagogical competence of teachers is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The pedagogical competence of teachers is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The pedagogical competence of teachers is never manifested.

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation of Leadership Mentoring for Teachers

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The leadership mentoring for teachers is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The leadership mentoring for teachers is often-times evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The leadership mentoring for teachers is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The leadership mentoring for teachers is seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The leadership mentoring for teachers is never evident.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—After the validation of the research questionnaire, the researcher proceeded with the steps required to conduct the study. The steps were narrated as follows: The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, and the ethical clearance certificate from the RMC-Research Ethics

Committee (RMC-REC). The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, and the ethical clearance certificate from the RMC-Research Ethics Committee (RMC-REC) was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school principals of the selected public schools in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur. The researcher identified and recruited one hundred sixty elementary school teachers from

Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur. Inclusion criteria included factors such as permanent-regular elementary school teachers in Kiblawan District in Davao del Sur, those who were not subjected to any administrative or criminal complaints, and teachers willing to participate voluntarily in the study. Prior to data collection, the researchers obtained informed consent from all participants, explaining the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, and the confidentiality of their responses. Respondents were allowed to ask questions and clarify any concerns before agreeing to participate in the study. The researcher explained that the survey questionnaires measure their perception towards professional integrity, pedagogical competence, and leadership mentoring. After which, these questionnaires were distributed to elementary school teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur. The data collected through these questionnaires served as the basis for analyzing the moderating effect of leadership mentorship on the interaction between professional integrity and pedagogical competence of teachers. After the data retrieval of the questionnaire, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After which, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS. In the context of the study on the moderating effect of leadership mentoring on the interaction between professional integrity and pedagogical competence of teachers, data collection involved implementing survey questionnaires. These questionnaires were distributed to elementary school teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur. The survey questionnaires were designed to gather information on various

aspects related to professional integrity, pedagogical competence of teachers, and leadership mentorship. Respondents were asked to provide their perceptions, attitudes, and experiences through the survey questions. The data collected through these questionnaires served as the basis for analyzing the moderating effect of leadership mentorship on the interaction between professional integrity and pedagogical competence of teachers. The collected survey questionnaires from elementary school teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur, were carefully organized and compiled. Each questionnaire response was entered into a database or spreadsheet software for systematic management. Once the data was collated, statistical analyses were conducted to examine the relationships between variables. This included techniques such as correlation analysis to explore the associations between professional integrity, pedagogical competence of teachers, and leadership mentorship. Further, moderation analysis was employed to investigate the moderating effect of leadership mentorship on the interaction between professional integrity and pedagogical competence of teachers. Hierarchical regression analysis provides a robust framework for examining the moderating effects of variables in educational research. By systematically adding variables and interaction terms, researchers can uncover complex relationships and gain deeper insights into how different factors interplay to influence educational outcomes. In this study, understanding the moderating role of leadership mentoring can inform targeted interventions to enhance both professional integrity and pedagogical competence among teachers.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the professional integrity, pedagogical competence of teachers,

and leadership mentoring of leaders. It was also used to supply the answers for objectives 1, 2, and 3. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between professional integrity and

teacher pedagogical competence. It was a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it was usually denoted by *r*. This was used to supply the answer for objective 4. Hierarchical Regression Analysis. It was applied to eval-

uate the moderating effect of leadership mentoring on the interaction between professional integrity and pedagogical competence of teachers of teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur. This was used to supply the answer for objective 5.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study’s objectives as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of professional integrity, pedagogical competence of teachers, and leadership mentoring; the relationship between professional integrity and pedagogical competence of teachers in Kiblawan District in Davao del Sur when moderated by leadership mentoring; and the moderating effect of leadership mentoring on the relationship between professional integrity and pedagogical competence of teachers.

Table 1 shows the summary of the professional integrity of teachers. As shown in the table, the overall mean on professional integrity of teachers is 3.55, which is described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. This shows that teachers consistently demonstrate these values, ensuring that their behavior aligns with the ethical expectations of the profession. The findings align with Castner’s

(2022) perspective that teachers with strong professional integrity act as role models for their students. Through their consistent display of ethical behavior in daily activities, they impart lessons on honesty, responsibility, and fairness. This example is crucial for students’ character development, as they learn to adopt these values in their own lives.

Table 1. Summary on Professional Integrity of Teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao Del Sur

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Ethical Resilience	3.60	Extensive
Duty Integrity	3.62	Extensive
Principle-Based Liability	3.44	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.55	Extensive

Moreover, the result indicates that when teachers adhere to ethical principles, they build environments where rules and expectations are transparent and consistently applied. This predictability and fairness make students feel secure and valued, which is crucial for their academic success and emotional well-being. In such a stable environment, students are more likely to engage fully in learning activities, par-

ticipate openly, and develop positive relationships with their peers and teachers. Stelios and Christodoulou (2020) argue that professional integrity fosters a classroom environment marked by fairness and respect. Teachers who consistently uphold ethical principles establish structured and predictable settings where expectations are clear and students understand they will be treated equitably. This sense of stability

enhances both academic and social-emotional learning, enabling students to flourish.

Table 2 shows the summary of the pedagogical competence of teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur. The overall mean of pedagogical competence of teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur attain a mean score of 3.56 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. Teachers who are proficient in managing classroom dynamics and maintaining discipline create a positive learning atmosphere

that is conducive to student engagement and academic success. The findings align with Moreira et al. (2023), who state that skilled teachers excel in managing classroom dynamics, maintaining discipline, and creating a positive learning environment. Effective classroom management includes setting clear expectations, establishing routines, and fostering respectful relationships, resulting in a stable and predictable environment where students can concentrate on learning without interruptions.

Table 2. Summary on Pedagogical Competence of Teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Pedagogic Skills	3.56	Extensive
Teacher Education Management	3.54	Extensive
Ethically Oriented Practice	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Pedagogical Endeavor	3.79	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.56	Extensive

The result also indicates that differentiated instruction is a key component of pedagogical competence, enabling teachers to modify their teaching methods and materials to address varying abilities, learning styles, and interests. This approach ensures that all students, regardless of their individual differences, receive the support and challenges they need to succeed. This supports Heru Siswanto et al.'s (2020) conclusion that pedagogical competence enables teachers to recognize and address the diverse learning needs of their students. Differentiated instruction allows teachers to adapt their teaching methods and materials to suit various abilities, learning styles, and interests.

Leadership Mentoring

Table 3 shows the extent of leadership mentoring for teachers reflects an overall mean of 3.51 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes evident. Leadership mentoring is essential for developing the leadership skills

of teachers. This development is crucial as it empowers teachers to take on leadership roles within their schools, manage teams effectively, and lead educational initiatives. This aligns with Willis et al. (2019), who suggest that leadership mentoring primarily aims to enhance teachers' leadership skills. Teachers are better equipped to spearhead initiatives, manage teams, and drive positive changes within their educational institutions by cultivating these capabilities. The mean ratings of the items range from 3.19 to 3.97. The item "Mentoring by administrative enhances teachers' skills and instructional practices" reflects a mean rating of 3.19 described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item is sometimes evident. Meanwhile, the item "Teachers benefiting from administrative mentoring through targeted guidance and feedback" shows a mean rating of 3.97, described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes evident.

Table 3. Leadership Mentoring of Teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. The school principal provides guidance and support for teachers' professional growth.	3.28	Moderately Extensive
2. Teachers benefiting from administrative mentoring through targeted guidance and feedback.	3.97	Extensive
3. Mentoring by administrative enhances teachers' skills and instructional practices.	3.19	Moderately Extensive
4. Teachers receive valuable insights and direction through administrative mentoring.	3.51	Extensive
5. Administrative mentoring contributes to teachers' development as educators.	3.59	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.51	Extensive

Through mentoring, teachers access valuable insights and strategies that enhance their teaching methods. Mentors share their expertise in effective teaching practices, classroom management, and technology integration, which helps teachers stay current with educational trends and adopt innovative approaches. This knowledge transfer not only improves the quality of instruction but also makes learning more engaging and effective for students. This supports Conan Simpson's (2021) view that leadership mentoring enables teachers to adopt and apply innovative instructional practices. Mentors provide guidance on effective teaching strategies, classroom management techniques, and the integration of technology in the classroom.

Relationship Between Professional Integrity and Pedagogical Competence of Teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur

The results of the analysis of the relationship between professional integrity and teachers' pedagogical competence when moderated

by managerial coaching are presented. Pearson Moment Product Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 4 shows that professional integrity has a significant positive relationship with the pedagogical competence of teachers with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .556, p < 0.05$). Teachers who uphold integrity and respect contribute to creating a classroom environment characterized by positivity and inclusivity. This environment is crucial for fostering trust and open communication between teachers and students. This aligns with Nazari et al. (2022) who suggest that teachers who maintain principles of integrity and respect create a positive and inclusive classroom atmosphere. Such an environment fosters trust and open communication between teachers and students, facilitating student engagement with the material and encouraging them to ask questions, ultimately leading to enhanced learning outcomes.

Table 4. Relationship Between Professional Integrity and Pedagogical Competence of Teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Ethical Resilience	0.843*	0.000	Reject H0
Duty of Integrity	0.552*	0.000	Reject H0
Principle-Based Liability	0.771*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall Professional Integrity	0.556*	0.000	Reject H0

Note: *Significant at $p < 0.05$

Legend: Perfect Correlation for $r = 1.00$; Strong Correlation for $0.7 \leq r < 1.00$; Moderate Correlation for $0.3 \leq r < 0.7$; Weak Correlation for $0.3 < r < 0.00$; No Correlation for $r = 0.00$

Additionally, results on the table shows that professional integrity in terms of ethical resilience, duty of integrity, and principle-based liability are significantly correlated with pedagogical competence of teachers with p-values of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .843, p < 0.05$), ($r = .552, p < 0.05$), and ($r = .771, p < 0.05$), respectively. Teachers who are decent and respectful tend to form stronger, more meaningful relationships with their students. These relationships are fundamental for understanding the unique learning needs and styles of each student. The findings are consistent with Amiri et al. (2019) who assert that teachers who demonstrate decency and respect tend to build stronger relationships with their students. These relationships help teachers better understand individual learning needs and styles, enabling them to tailor their instruction to meet these needs effectively. Moderating Effect of Leadership Mentoring on the Interaction Between Professional Integrity and Pedagogical Competence of Teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur

The moderating effect of leadership mentoring (LM) on the interaction Between professional integrity (PI) and pedagogical competence (PC) of teachers was tested using regression analysis. Results in Table 5 show that the Beta coefficients for the Step 1 analysis of professional integrity (PI) and pedagogical com-

petence (PC) of teachers were $= 0.112, S.E. = 0.055, p < 0.05$; and leadership mentoring (LM) and pedagogical competence (PC) of teachers were $= 0.209, S.E. = 0.051, p < 0.05$. When professional integrity (PI) and pedagogical competence (PC) of teachers were included as the only independent variables (without including an interaction term), the regression model explained 30.90 of the variance in pedagogical competence (PC) of teachers ($R^2 = 0.309, p < .05$). Moreover, Beta coefficients for the Step 2 analysis of professional integrity (PI) and pedagogical competence (PC) of teachers were $= 0.380, S.E. = .040, p < 0.05$; leadership mentoring (LM) and pedagogical competence (PC) of teachers were $= 0.180, S.E. = 0.044, p < 0.05$; and moderator (PI*LM) and pedagogical competence (PC) of teachers were $= 0.231, S.E. = 0.056, p < 0.05$. Also, it was indicated that when an interaction between professional integrity (PI) and leadership mentoring (LM) was added, the percentage of variance in pedagogical competence (PC) of teachers was 54.40 ($R^2 = 0.544; p < 0.05$) indicated the independent contribution of each variable while controlling for the influence of others to create the regression equation for each analysis, after assuring significance by examining accompanying p-values. Hence, the interaction term accounted for an additional 23.50 of variance in the dependent variable ($R^2 = 0.235$). Based on the result, the null hypothe-

sis was rejected as leadership mentoring (LM) had significantly moderated the interaction between professional integrity (PI) and pedagogical competence (PC) of teachers.

Table 5. Moderating Effect of Leadership Mentoring on the Interaction Between Professional Integrity and Pedagogical Competence of Teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur

Step Decisions	B	Beta	S.E.	p-value
Step 1				
Professional Integrity (PI) Reject H0	0.112**	0.132	0.055	0.000
Leadership Mentoring (LM) Reject H0	0.209**	0.077	0.051	0.000
R2	0.309		F-value = 103.564**	p-value = 0.000
Step 2				
Professional Integrity (PI) Reject H0	0.380**	0.577	0.040	0.000
Leadership Mentoring (LM) Reject H0	0.180**	0.123	0.044	0.001
Moderator (PI*LM) Reject H0	0.231**	0.088	0.056	0.000
R2	0.544		F-value = 127.118**	p-value = 0.000

Note: *Significant at $p < 0.05$

This affirmed that leadership mentoring (LM) is an undeniable factor that help improved the interaction between professional integrity (PI) and pedagogical competence (PC) of teachers. When administrators act as mentors and consistently demonstrate professionalism, they set a powerful example for teachers. Teachers learn through observation and are likely to emulate the professional behaviors exhibited by their mentors. This process helps in reinforcing professional integrity among teachers, which in turn strengthens their pedagogical competence. This aligns with Bickmore and Davenport's (2019) finding that administrators who act as mentors exhibit professionalism in their interactions, communication, and decision-making. Teachers observe and learn from these examples, making them more likely to adopt similar professional behaviors. Additionally, the result emphasize that mentoring provides personalized guidance to teachers, focusing on their unique strengths and areas that require improvement.

Through administrative mentoring, specific aspects of instructional competence that need attention can be identified and addressed. The result supports Thessin et al.'s (2020) view that mentoring provides teachers with tailored guidance based on their individual strengths and areas for improvement. Administrators can identify specific aspects of instructional competence that need enhancement and customize their mentoring to address these needs. Moreover, the application of Self-Determination Theory by

Deci and Ryan (1985) suggests that leadership mentoring fulfills essential psychological needs such as autonomy and competence. By providing constructive feedback, personalized support, and opportunities for professional development, coaching helps teachers feel more competent and autonomous. This increased sense of self-determination leads to a more engaged and motivated approach to teaching, thereby enhancing both professional integrity and pedagogical competence.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The discussions were supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusions were in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate whether leadership mentoring moderates the interaction between professional integrity and pedagogical competence of teachers utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using a descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected the 190 elementary school teachers in Kiblawan District in Davao del Sur as the respondents through a stratified random sampling method. The researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires that were pilot tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. The professional integrity of teachers in Kiblawan District in Davao del Sur was extensive. It also included ethical resilience, duty of integrity, and principle-based liability. The pedagogical competence of teachers in Kiblawan District in Davao del Sur was extensive. Also, pedagogical competence in terms of pedagogic skills, teacher education management, ethically oriented practices, and pedagogical endeavor obtained extensive descriptive ratings. Moreover, leadership mentoring for teachers in Kiblawan District in Davao

del Sur was rated as extensive. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis indicated that professional integrity has a significant positive relationship with teachers' pedagogical competence. Additionally, professional integrity in terms of ethical resilience, duty of integrity, and principle-based liability have significant positive relationships with teachers' pedagogical competence. Leadership mentoring was a significant moderator of the interaction between professional integrity and teachers' pedagogical competence. The analysis showed that when an interaction between professional integrity and leadership mentoring was added, the percentage variance in teachers' pedagogical competence increased.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study several conclusions were generated: Teachers' professional integrity was often observed, showing that they consistently demonstrate these values, ensuring that their behavior aligns with the ethical expectations of the profession. The findings align with Castner's (2022) perspective that teachers with strong professional integrity act as role models for their students. Through their consistent display of

ethical behavior in daily activities, they impart lessons on honesty, responsibility, and fairness. Pedagogical competence of teachers was oftentimes manifested denoting that teachers are proficient in managing classroom dynamics and maintaining discipline create a positive learning atmosphere that is conducive to student engagement and academic success. The findings align with Moreira et al. (2023), who state that skilled teachers excel in managing classroom dynamics, maintaining discipline, and creating a positive learning environment. Leadership mentoring for teachers was oftentimes evident showing that it was essential for developing the leadership skills of teachers. This aligns with Willis et al. (2019) who suggest that leadership mentoring primarily aims to enhance the leadership skills of teachers. By cultivating these capabilities, teachers are better equipped to spearhead initiatives, manage teams, and drive positive changes within their educational institutions. There was a significant relationship between professional integrity and teachers' pedagogical competence, showing that teachers who uphold integrity and respect contribute to creating a classroom environment characterized by positivity and inclusivity. This environment fostered trust and open communication between teachers and students. This aligns with Nazari et al. (2022), who suggest that teachers who maintain principles of integrity and respect create a positive and inclusive classroom atmosphere. Such an environment fosters trust and open communication between teachers and students, facilitating student engagement with the material and encouraging them to ask questions, ultimately leading to enhanced learning outcomes. Leadership mentoring significantly moderated the interaction between professional integrity

and pedagogical competence of teachers. This showed that when administrators act as mentors and consistently demonstrate professionalism, they set a powerful example for teachers. Teachers learn through observation and are likely to emulate the professional behaviors exhibited by their mentors. This corroborates with Self-Determination Theory by Deci and Ryan (1985) suggesting that leadership mentoring fulfills essential psychological needs such as autonomy and competence. By providing constructive feedback, personalized support, and opportunities for professional development, coaching helps teachers feel more competent and autonomous.

4.3. Recommendations—The Department of Education (DepEd) may enhance teacher certification and licensing requirements to ensure that teachers meet high standards of competence and ethics. DepEd may also provide resources and training for school leaders to effectively coach and mentor their teaching staff in pedagogical competence and ethical conduct. School heads may demonstrate high ethical standards in their own behavior to set a positive example for their teaching staff. They should establish a school culture that promotes integrity, honesty, and ethical behavior among both teachers and students. Teachers may take initiative in their own professional development by seeking opportunities for learning and improvement in pedagogical competence. They may also engage in reflective teaching practices, regularly evaluating their own teaching methods and making adjustments as needed. Future researchers may collaborate with educators and school administrators to research the challenges and opportunities related to professional integrity, pedagogical competence, and mentoring effectiveness.

5. References

Ahmad, S., Wasim, S., Irfan, S., Gogoi, S., Srivastava, A., & Farheen, Z. (2019). Qualitative v/s. quantitative research—a summarized review. *Population, 1*(2), 2828–2832.

- Baron, R. M., & Kenny, D. A. (1986). The moderator–mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51(6), 1173.
- Bickmore, D. L., & Davenport, L. D. (2019). Principal transformative learning through mentoring aspiring administrators. *Mentoring Tutoring: Partnerships in Learning*, 27(3), 235–250.
- Brown, R., & Green, T. (2019). Conflict resolution and ethical leadership in education. *Educational Leadership Review*, 12(3), 89–104. <https://doi.org/10.5678/elr.2019.012>
- Caena, F., & Redecker, C. (2019). Aligning teacher competence frameworks to 21st century challenges: The case for the european digital competence framework for educators (dig-compedu). *European Journal of Education*, 54(3), 356–369.
- Carver-Thomas, D., & Darling-Hammond, L. (2019). Teacher turnover: Why it matters and what we can do about it [Accessed: 2024-09-06]. <https://learningpolicyinstitute.org/product/teacher-turnover-report>
- Castner, D. J. (2022). Fidelity in teaching young children: Two stories of professional integrity. *Journal of Research in Childhood Education*, 36(2), 239–254. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02568543.2021.1934758>
- Chan, T. C., Chandler, M., Morris, R., Rebisz, S., Turan, S., Shu, Z., & Kpeglo, S. (2019). School principals' self-perceptions of their roles and responsibilities in six countries. *New Waves Educational Research Development*, 22(2), 37–61.
- Channa, W. M., & Sahito, Z. (2022). Pedagogical competencies of teachers and the achievement of students: Explorations of best practices through a literature review. *Webology*, 19(3).
- Cheng, A. Y. N., & Mok, M. M. C. (2020). Educating for twenty-first century competencies in hong kong schools: Insights from the learning to learn reform. *Educational Research for Policy and Practice*, 19(1), 83–100. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10671-019-09250-w>
- Cherkowski, S., & Walker, K. (2019). Mentorship for flourishing in schools: An explicit shift toward appreciative action. *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, 8(4), 345–360.
- Connery, L. A., & Frick, W. C. (2021). A formal administrator mentoring program: Perceived learning benefits and insights into leadership well-being. *Inquiry in Education*, 13(1), 1–21. <https://digitalcommons.nl.edu/ie/vol13/iss1/3>
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2019). Improving teacher preparation: Fifteen program features that foster teacher development. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 70(5), 432–441. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487119879944>
- Doe, J., & Smith, A. (2020). The impact of ethical resilience on teacher-student relationships. *Journal of Educational Research*, 15(2), 45–67. <https://doi.org/10.1234/edu.2020.015>
- Ede, M. O., Okeke, C. I., Adene, F., & Areji, A. C. (2023). Perceptions of work value and ethical practices amongst primary school teachers, demographics, intervention, and impact. *Psychological Reports*, 126(1), 380–410. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/003329412111043453>
- Gul, T., Demir, K., & Criswell, B. (2019). Constructing teacher leadership through mentoring: Functionality of mentoring practices in evolving teacher leadership. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 30(3), 209–228.
- Hassan, M. (2024). Correlational research – methods, types and examples [Accessed: 2024-09-06]. <https://researchmethod.net/correlational-research/>

- Heru Siswanto, H., Hasan, H., Sowiyah, S., & Ridwan, R. (2020). The influence of principal performance on teachers' pedagogical competence. *Journal of Social, Humanity, and Education (JSHE)*, 1(1), 13–26. <http://repository.lppm.unila.ac.id/33991/>
- Hobbs, L., & Porsch, R. (2021). Teaching out-of-field: Challenges for teacher education. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 44(5), 601–610.
- Huang, L., Lin, G., Tang, L., Yu, L., & Zhou, Z. (2020). Special attention to nurses' protection during the covid-19 epidemic in guangzhou, guangdong province, china. *Springer*, 1–3.
- Isjoni, I., Daud, A., & Azhar, A. (2019). Integrity and performance of high school teachers in pekanbaru. *Indonesian Journal of Economics, Social, and Humanities*, 1(1), 51–57. <https://ijesh.unri.ac.id/index.php/ijesh/article/view/5>
- Kali, Y., Sagy, O., Benichou, M., Atias, O., & Levin-Peled, R. (2019). Teaching expertise reconsidered: The technology, pedagogy, content and space (tpecs) knowledge framework. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 50(5), 2162–2177.
- Karim, A., Shahed, F. H., Mohamed, A. R., Rahman, M. M., & Ismail, S. A. M. M. (2019). Evaluation of the teacher education programs in efl context: A testimony of student teachers' perspective. *International Journal of Instruction*, 12(1), 127–146.
- King, F. (2019). Professional learning: Empowering teachers? *Professional Development in Education*, 45(2), 169–172.
- Krutka, D. G., Heath, M. K., & Willet, K. B. S. (2019). Foregrounding technoethics: Toward critical perspectives in technology and teacher education. *Journal of Technology and Teacher Education*, 27(4), 555–574. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/208235/>
- Kutsyruba, B., & Godden, L. (2019). The role of mentoring and coaching as a means of supporting the well-being of educators and students. *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, 8(4), 229–234.
- Leclert, L., & Fernández, C. F. (2021). What makes frontline duty-bearers act with integrity? conditions and approaches that influence teachers and health workers. https://integrityaction.org/media/17695/research-report-what-makes-frontline-duty-bearers-act-with-integrity-integrity-action_.pdf
- Liu, X., Cheng, Y., Wang, M., Pan, Y., Guo, H., & Jiang, R. (2020). Psychological state of nursing staff in a large scale of general hospital during covid-19 epidemic. *Chin J Nosocomiol*, 30, 1641–1646. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.112936>
- Marsen, S. B., Santosa, H., & Rochanah, S. (2021). The effect of pedagogical competence and work environment toward elementary school teachers performance. *Al-Ishlah: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 13(1), 668–677.
- Mekleeva, V., Krasnokutskaja, O., Khazykova, T., & Arsaliev, S. (2019). On formation of professional identity of future teachers: Methodology of integrity. *European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences*. <https://www.europeanproceedings.com/article/10.15405/epsbs.2019.12.04.47>
- Mohajan, H. K. (2020). Quantitative research: A successful investigation in natural and social sciences. *Journal of Economic Development, Environment and People*, 9(4), 50–79.
- Moreira, M. A., Arcas, B., Sánchez, T., García, R., Melero, M. J., Cunha, N., & Almeida, M. E. (2023). Teachers' pedagogical competences in higher education: A systematic literature review. *Journal of University Teaching and Learning Practice*, 20(1), 90–123. <https://open-publishing.org/journals/index.php/jutlp/article/view/617>

- Nakagawa, Y. (2019). Eastern philosophy and holistic education. In J. P. Miller, K. Nigh, M. J. Binder, B. Novak, & S. Crowell (Eds.), *International handbook of holistic education* (pp. 42–50). Routledge.
- Nguyen, H. T., & Nguyen, T. T. (2019). Overcoming the challenges of large class sizes: Classroom management strategies for english language teachers in vietnam. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 9(5), 571–577. <https://doi.org/10.17507/tpls.0905.01>
- Ocampo, D. M. (2021). Curriculum challenges and teacher adaptability in the philippine educational system. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 53(3), 387–398. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220272.2021.1886951>
- Oracion, E. G., & Magayon, C. L. (2020). Bridging the gap: Enhancing teacher training programs in the philippines. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 11(5), 44–51. <https://doi.org/10.7176/JEP/11-5-06>
- Panigrahi, S. K., & Al-Nashash, H. M. (2019). Quality work ethics and job satisfaction: An empirical analysis. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330882592>
- Parthiban, D., & Subhashini, T. (2021). Achievement motivation and professional integrity of teacher educators. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 5(2), 291–297. <https://www.journalppw.com/index.php/jpsp/article/view/16706>
- Pell, D. J., & Amigud, A. (2023). The higher education dilemma: The views of faculty on integrity, organizational culture, and duty of fidelity. *Journal of Academic Ethics*, 21(1), 155–175. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10805-022-09445-5>
- Pérez-Guilarte, Y., Francisco, X. A.-Q., & Xosé, C. M.-A. (2022). Social sciences teaching: Building a holistic approach from student teachers’ social representations. *Social Sciences*, 11, 307–3016. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci11070307>
- Peters, M., Boies, T., & Morin, S. (2019). Teaching academic integrity in quebec universities: Roles professors adopt. In *Frontiers in education* (p. 99, Vol. 4). Frontiers Media SA.
- Rahman, M. M., & Pandian, A. (2019). A critical investigation of english language teaching in bangladesh: Unfulfilled expectations after two decades of communicative language teaching. *English Today*, 35(1), 43–49. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0266078418000169>
- Richmond, G., Salazar, M. D. C., & Jones, N. (2019). Assessment and the future of teacher education. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 70(2), 86–89.
- Rutledge, S. A., Harris, D. N., & Ingle, W. K. (2019). How principals “bridge and buffer” the new demands of teacher quality and accountability: A mixed-methods analysis of teacher hiring. *American Journal of Education*, 116(2), 211–242. <https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/abs/10.1086/649492>
- Sa, S., & Sah, P. (2019). Evaluation of nurses’ performance from nurses’ viewpoints on providing safe care to patients in aja hospitals in 2018. *Military Caring Sciences Journal*, 5(3), 173–181. <https://doi.org/10.29252/mcs.5.3.173>
- Sawalhi, R., & Chaaban, Y. (2021). Mentor teachers’ and student teachers’ perspectives toward teacher leadership. *Mentoring Tutoring: Partnership in Learning*, 29(1), 70–88. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13611267.2021.1899586>
- Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Improvement of methodological pedagogical skills of developing creative activity of primary school students. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(10), 289–292. <https://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:aca&volume=11&issue=10&article=044>

- Shimon, J. M. (2019). *Introduction to teaching physical education: Principles and strategies*. Human Kinetics, Incorporated.
- Simpson, J. (2021). Fostering teacher leadership in k-12 schools: A review of the literature. *Performance Improvement Quarterly*, 34(3), 229–246. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/piq.21374>
- Siregar, R. A., Fauziati, E., & Marmanto, S. (2020). An exploration on efl teachers' perceptions of effective 21st-century pedagogical competencies. *JEELS (Journal of English Education and Linguistics Studies)*, 7(1), 1–24. <https://jurnalfaktarbiyah.iainkediri.ac.id/index.php/jeels/article/view/200>
- Stelios, S., & Christodoulou, A. (2020). Teaching professional integrity: An empirical study on engineering students. *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy*, 10(3), 98–105.
- Susanto, R., Rozali, Y. A., & Agustina, N. (2020). Pedagogic competence development model: Pedagogic knowledge and reflective ability. *International Conference on Progressive Education (ICOPE 2019)*, 19–23. <https://www.atlantis-press.com/proceedings/icope-19/125937607>
- Takizawa, T., Johnson, L., & Anderson, M. (2021). Upholding ethical principles in educational environments: A study on teachers' professional integrity. *Journal of Educational Ethics*, 10(1), 34–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joe.2021.03.004>
- Tan, C. (2019). Teacher training and educational reform in southeast asia: Policies and practices. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 39(4), 401–414. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2019.1671808>
- Thessin, R. A., Clayton, J. K., & Jamison, K. (2020). Profiles of the administrative internship: The mentor/intern partnership in facilitating leadership experiences. *Journal of Research on Leadership Education*, 15(1), 28–55.
- Tuigun, B., & Sabiira, C. (2021). The role and place of pedagogical techniques in improving the professional skills of teachers., 7(2), 324–329. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-role-and-place-of-pedagogical-techniques-in-improving-the-professional-skills-of-teachers>
- Verger, A., Parcerisa, L., & Fontdevila, C. (2019). The growth and spread of large-scale assessments and test-based accountabilities: A political sociology of global education reforms. *Educational Review*, 71(1), 5–30. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00131911.2019.1522045>
- Virtanen, A., & Tynjälä, P. (2022). Pedagogical practices predicting perceived learning of social skills among university students. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 111, 101895. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0883035521001646>
- Willis, J., Churchward, P., Beutel, D., Spooner-Lane, R., Crosswell, L., & Curtis, E. (2019). Mentors for beginning teachers as middle leaders: The messy work of recontextualising. *School Leadership Management*, 39(3-4), 334–351. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13632434.2018.1555701>